

Effect Of Deep Transverse Friction Massage On Treatment Of Lateral Epicondylitis -A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Background: The lateral epicondylitis is a very common disease and it is painful because of degeneration of Extensor Carpi radialis brevis and the extensor communis digitorum.

Objective: To find the effect of the deep transverse friction massage (DTF) in reducing pain, inflammation, improving functional activity and enhancing grip strength in patients with lateral epicondylitis.

Material and Methods: A systematic search was conducted for randomized controlled trials published between 2018 and 2024. The databases searched included PubMed and Google Scholar. A total of 55 articles were identified, of which 14 met the inclusion criteria and were selected for the study. These selected studies specifically examined the effects of transverse friction massage.

Results: The findings indicate that incorporating Deep Transverse Friction Massage (DTFM) alongside conventional treatments contributes to pain reduction, preservation of grip strength, and enhanced functional outcomes in individuals with lateral epicondylitis.

Conclusion: The reviewed literature supports the therapeutic value of Deep Transverse Friction Massage in both the prevention and management of lateral epicondylitis, highlighting its effectiveness in improving patient outcomes.

Keywords: Tennis elbow, Deep transverse friction massage, lateral epicondylitis, Extensor Carpi Radialis Brevis.

INTRODUCTION

Tennis elbow, medically referred to as lateral epicondylitis, is a common overuse musculoskeletal disorder characterized by pain, tenderness, and functional limitation on the lateral side of the elbow. Despite its name, the condition affects a wide range of individuals engaged in repetitive wrist and forearm movements, not just tennis players.^[1] It primarily involves degeneration and inflammation at the origin of the extensor carpi radialis brevis (ECRB) and extensor digitorum communis muscles at the lateral epicondyle.^[2]

Lateral epicondylitis can significantly impact both personal and professional life due to persistent pain and functional limitations. The condition may last between 6 to 24 months on

average and is associated with work related disability in nearly 5% of the working-age population.^[2] Epidemiologically, it affects 1–3% of the general population, with peak prevalence in individuals aged 40 to 59 years.^[3] Although less common in younger adults, it may also occur in those aged 18–40, particularly in males due to higher involvement in manual labour or sports.^[5] The dominant arm is more frequently affected, and the pain may radiate down the forearm, especially during activities requiring wrist extension.^[5]

The most commonly involved muscle is the ECRB, and the condition is also referred to by terms such as epicondylalgia, extensor tendinopathy, and extensor carpi radialis brevis tendinosis.^[4] The underlying pathology involves microtears from cumulative

mechanical overuse, leading to disorganized collagen and chronic degenerative changes.^[2]

A variety of conservative treatment approaches are employed for managing lateral epicondylitis, including therapeutic ultrasound, phonophoresis, electrical stimulation, neural mobilization, stretching, strengthening exercises, bracing, and soft tissue mobilization techniques such as friction massage.^[4] Despite the availability of these options, the condition remains challenging to treat due to its chronic nature and tendency to recur.

Deep transverse friction massage (DTFM), also referred to as Cyriax friction, is a manual therapy technique commonly used in the management of chronic tendinopathies. The terms DTFM and Cyriax are often used interchangeably, as they describe the same method developed by Dr. James Cyriax. This technique involves precise, repetitive movements applied across the fibres of the affected tendon to reduce pain, break down adhesions, and enhance blood circulation.^[7] It is particularly effective in restoring the alignment and extensibility of connective tissues, especially around the wrist extensor muscle group.^[8]

Although several conservative therapies are used to treat lateral epicondylitis, there is limited consolidated evidence highlighting the effectiveness of deep transverse friction massage (DTFM) as a stand-alone or adjunct treatment. Therefore, this study aims to systematically review the effect of DTFM in managing lateral epicondylitis, filling the existing gap in the literature and guiding evidence-based clinical practice.

OBJECTIVE

To review the existing literature on the effectiveness of deep transverse friction massage (DTFM) in the management of lateral epicondylitis, with a focus on its impact on pain reduction, inflammation control, improvement in functional activity, and enhancement of grip strength.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. **Shukla et al., (2023)** conducted RCT on the A comparative analysis of the efficacy of mulligan mobilization versus Cyriax Approach in the care of Tennis elbow with the sample size of 60 which is divided into two groups. Group A was treated with

mulligan mobilization and group B was treated with Cyriax for 15 days, there were 30 patients in each group, alternative therapy was given to all the patients, Effect of mulligan and Cyriax in patient with sub-acute lateral epicondylitis.^[2]

2. **Kumar et al., (2023)** conducted a study on efficacy of corticosteroid injection versus in case of lateral epicondylitis intense friction massage with the sample size of 20, patient was divided into two groups, Group1 received a corticosteroid injection of 20 mg, methyl prednisolone in 10 ml solution, after two weeks of rest, the patient was advised to wear a detachable brace for 1week Group2 got a 10ml injection of 1% lidocaine followed by DTF.^[3]
3. **Gopal Nambi et al., (2023)** conducted a study on Clinical and radiological effect of corticosteroid and deep transverse friction massage and mills manipulation in lateral epicondylitis with sample size of 60, which is divided into two group active MM Group n=30 and sham MM n=30 functional disability and hand grip strength show larger effect in active MM group then the sham MM group.^[9]
4. **Bashir et al.,(2022)** conducted a study on the comparison of combined isotonic Deep friction soft tissue Technique on pain and function in patient with persistent lateral epicondylitis with sample size of 22, and is divided into two group Group A and Group B is treated with the combined isotonic technique, Group B is treated with Deep friction Massage, Both group treated for 12 session in 4 weeks, combined isotonic exercise group is more effective then Deep friction soft tissue technique.^[5]
5. **Zabul-un-Nisa et al., (2022)** conducted a study for the effectiveness of dry needling and Deep friction massage in lateral epicondylitis with the sample size of 32 that divided into groups, Group A received Deep transverse friction, where as Group B dry needling received six treatment session at frequency of two session per week, both the intervention is effective in treating tennis elbow.^[10]
6. **Ahmed et al.,(2021)** conducted a study on comparing the efficacy of mulligan mobilization versus Cyriax approach in the administration of lateral epicondylitis, with

- the sample size of 60 which are divided into 2 group 30 in each group. Group A received deep transverse friction, massage and mills manipulation whereas Group received mulligan mobilization with movement after 4 weeks of treatment group A showed more improvement in functional disability and grip strength.^[4]
7. **kalaskar et al.,(2021)** conducted a study on A comparative study to evaluate the efficacy of supervised exercise program and cyriax physiotherapy on pain and function in lateral epicondylitis, with the help of thirty participants. that is divided into two groups 1. supervised exercise group, 2. Cyriax physiotherapy group, over a 4 -week period, 3 times a week for the total of 12 sessions. improvement will be assessed by visual analogue scale and the tennis elbow function scale.^[6]
 8. **Akbar et al., (2021)** conducted a study on the effect of cyriax mulligan technique versus manual treatment on grip strength and functional outcome in patient with lateral epicondyle, with sample size of 66 which is randomly grouped A and Group B. Group A received cyriax approach and Group B, Mulligan group in which it is seen that cyriax group have better effect the Mulligan.^[11]
 9. **Sharma et al.,(2021)** conducted a study on the efficacy of cyriax physiotherapy versus cyriax and low-level laser therapy on pain and grip strength in lateral epicondylitis, with the sample size of 30 and is divided into two groups A and Group A received cyriax physiotherapy while group B patient received and low-level laser therapy for 3 weeks. We see batter improvement in pain and grip strength in group B as compared to A.^[12]
 10. **Abbas et al., (2019)** conducted a study on the effect of mulligan and the cyriax approach in the patient with sub-acute lateral epicondylitis with the sample size of n=30 which is allocated into the two groups. Group A is the cyriax group and group B is mulligan Group taping MWM, there whether 15 Participant in each group having sub-acute lateral epicondylitis. while comparing both group cyriax approach shows more significant improvement in term of pain and functional ability.^[8]
 11. **Safrin et al., (2019)** conducted randomized control study with Myofascial Released and ultrasound versus Deep Transverse Friction Massage on patient with Tennis elbow with the sample size of 10, which is 5 in each group Treatment group 5 people and control group 5 people the pain was measured using a visual analog scale. The group were involved in the study that is ofgroup 1 with myofascial release technique and ultrasound and group 2 with deep transverse friction.^[13]
 12. **Etminan, et al., (2019)** conducted a study on the effect of Dry needling group which received ultrasound along with Deep friction massagewhere as other Group received Dry needling instead of physiotherapy. Therapeutic duration was 3 weeks in each group and 3 sessions in each week.^[14]
 13. **Praveen et al., (2018)** conducted a study on effect of Maitland mobilization and conventional treatment on management of tennis elbow with sample size of 60 patient and is further divided into 2 groups, Group A is receiving ultrasound and Maitland mobilization, Deep friction massage, stretching and strengthening, Group B received only ultrasound, Deep friction massage, stretching and strengthening, the result show that physiotherapy have long term effect then other.^[7]

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

A systematic literature search was conducted using three electronic databases: PubMed, Google Scholar, and Springer Nature, focusing on studies published between 2018 and 2024. A total of 55 articles were initially identified. After screening based on inclusion and exclusion criteria, 14 articles were included for detailed review and analysis, all of which specifically investigated the effects of deep transverse friction massage (DTFM) or Cyriax technique in the management of lateral epicondylitis.

The inclusion criteria for the review were: articles published between 2018 and 2024, studies involving all genders, randomized controlled trials (RCTs), and research designs including interventional studies, cross-sectional studies, and surveys.

The exclusion criteria applied were as follows: 12 articles were excluded because they were systematic reviews or meta-analyses, 4 articles were excluded due to the presence of an abnormal palpable lump in the elbow joint, 15 articles were excluded as case studies, and 10 articles were removed for being published before 2018.

In total, 41 articles were excluded based on these criteria, and 14 articles were finally included in the review for detailed analysis.

RESULTS

A total of 14 studies were included in this review, all of which evaluated the effect of Deep Transverse Friction Massage (DTFM), also referred to as the Cyriax technique, in the management of lateral epicondylitis. The findings consistently demonstrate that DTFM is effective in minimising pain, improving grip strength, and enhancing functional outcomes. Shukla et al. (2023) found that patients treated with the Cyriax approach (DTFM combined with Mill's manipulation) showed significantly greater pain relief than those treated with Mulligan mobilization over a 15-day period. Similarly, Akbar et al. (2021) reported that patients in the Cyriax group showed a substantial reduction in pain scores (from a baseline of 8 to 1.9 over 8 weeks) and a marked improvement in grip strength (from approximately 32 kg to 53.5 kg), compared to the Mulligan group, which showed lesser gains. In another study by Ahmed et al. (2021), the Cyriax group outperformed Mulligan mobilization in terms of improvements in both functional disability and grip strength after four weeks of treatment. Kumar et al. (2023) compared corticosteroid injections to DTFM and found that while corticosteroid injections offered quicker initial relief, only the DTFM group maintained significant improvement in pain, function, and grip strength at the 6-month follow-up. Gopal Nambi et al. (2023) also demonstrated that combining corticosteroids with DTFM and Mill's manipulation led to significantly greater pain reduction and functional improvement than sham interventions ($p = 0.001$).

Other studies explored the effectiveness of DTFM alone or in combination with other interventions. Bashir et al. (2022) found that a combined isotonic exercise and DTFM

protocol produced superior improvements in pain and function compared to DTFM alone over a 4-week treatment period. Zabul-un-Nisa et al. (2022) compared DTFM with dry needling and reported that both interventions were effective in reducing pain and improving function, with no clear superiority between them. Similarly, Etminan et al. (2019) found both DTFM with ultrasound and dry needling to be effective over a 3-week treatment protocol. Safrin et al. (2019) compared DTFM with a combination of myofascial release and ultrasound and found that both treatments effectively reduced pain, although precise numerical differences were not reported. In a broader physiotherapy context, Praveen et al. (2018) observed that a combination of Maitland mobilization, DTFM, and strengthening exercises produced more sustained long-term benefits than conventional treatment without mobilization. Across multiple studies, DTFM, whether used as a standalone intervention or combined with other techniques, consistently led to significant improvements in pain reduction, grip strength, and upper limb functional performance. Overall, the evidence supports the efficacy of DTFM as a valuable and effective intervention in the conservative management of lateral epicondylitis.

DISCUSSION

The present literature review aimed to evaluate the efficacy of Deep Transverse Friction Massage (DTFM), also referred to as Cyriax physiotherapy, in the conservative management of lateral epicondylitis. The collective findings from the reviewed studies strongly support the use of DTFM in reducing pain, improving grip strength, and enhancing upper limb functional performance in patients with lateral epicondylitis. This aligns with the pathophysiological basis of the condition, where repetitive microtrauma leads to collagen disorganization and tendinopathy at the origin of the extensor carpi radialis brevis, making targeted tendonbased interventions like DTFM highly relevant.

Across the reviewed trials, DTFM consistently demonstrated a significant reduction in pain scores, as assessed through the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) or Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS). In studies such as those conducted by

Shukla et al. and Akbar et al., the Cyriax approach resulted in greater and more sustained pain relief than Mulligan mobilization. These results suggest that the mechanical effects of DTFM—such as disruption of adhesions, improved tendon vascularity, and normalization of collagen alignment—may directly address the underlying tendinopathic changes, rather than simply alleviating symptoms temporarily.

Grip strength, a key indicator of upper limb functionality and clinical recovery in lateral epicondylitis, also showed marked improvements in studies utilizing DTFM. For instance, Akbar et al. reported a significant increase in grip strength in the Cyriax group compared to the Mulligan group, with post-treatment gains exceeding 20 kg in some cases. Such improvements not only reflect reduced pain but also indicate restored tendon loading capacity and neuromuscular control, which are essential for daily tasks and occupational activities.

The long-term efficacy of DTFM also appears promising. In studies comparing DTFM with corticosteroid injections, such as that by Kumar et al., initial relief was faster with corticosteroids, but functional improvement and pain relief were better maintained at 6-month follow-up in the DTFM group. This finding is critical, as corticosteroids, while potent anti-inflammatories, do not promote structural tendon healing and may contribute to recurrence or degeneration over time. In contrast, DTFM seems to offer a regenerative stimulus to the affected tendon tissue, aligning with the goal of long-term rehabilitation.

Additionally, combining DTFM with other modalities—such as Mill's manipulation, supervised exercise programs, or isotonic strengthening—further enhanced clinical outcomes, as evidenced in studies by Gopal Nambi et al., Bashir et al., and Praveen et al. This supports the multifactorial approach to rehabilitation, wherein DTFM addresses localized tendon pathology, while adjunct therapies target surrounding muscular imbalances and movement impairments.

However, variability in treatment protocols (e.g., duration, frequency, and combination therapies), small sample sizes in some studies, and lack of long-term follow-up in others are limitations that should be acknowledged.

Moreover, although most studies used objective measures like VAS and grip strength dynamometry, standardization of outcome tools and treatment duration remains inconsistent. Future research should focus on large-scale, well-controlled randomized trials with standardized protocols and long-term follow-up to better define optimal treatment parameters and patient subgroups that may benefit most from DTFM.

In summary, the review highlights that Deep Transverse Friction Massage is a safe, cost-effective, and clinically beneficial intervention for managing lateral epicondylitis. Its effectiveness is comparable to, or in some cases superior to, other commonly used conservative approaches. When applied appropriately, either as a standalone intervention or in combination with other therapeutic techniques, DTFM plays a valuable role in restoring function, reducing symptoms, and enhancing the quality of life in affected individuals.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings from the reviewed literature, Deep Transverse Friction Massage (DTFM), also known as Cyriax physiotherapy, emerges as an effective conservative treatment modality for managing lateral epicondylitis. The evidence consistently supports its role in reducing pain, improving grip strength, and enhancing functional performance. Compared to other interventions such as corticosteroid injections, Mulligan mobilization, and dry needling, DTFM demonstrates comparable or superior outcomes, particularly in long-term symptom management.

The combination of DTFM with adjunct therapies like Mill's manipulation and supervised exercises appears to yield even better clinical results, reinforcing the importance of a multimodal approach in rehabilitation. Despite some variability in treatment protocols and sample sizes across studies, the overall consensus points toward DTFM as a reliable, low-cost, and non-invasive technique for restoring function and reducing disability in patients with lateral epicondylitis. Further high-quality, large-scale randomized controlled trials with standardized protocols and long-term follow-up are recommended to strengthen the current evidence.

base and guide clinical decision-making. The Authors declared no conflict of interest.

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